

MENTAL HEALTH MONITORING THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

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Abstract

There has also been a rise in psychological distress worldwide. An important medium that has asserted itself in this regard is social media. This has enabled people to share their feelings in a realistic manner. This large amount of user-generated content has opened the door for computational analysis. But diagnosing mental problems like depression, anxiety, and stress from their posts in a social media forum has remained a challenge. Traditional techniques in the lexis based approach and traditional machine learning algorithms have already been used for the purpose of sentiment classification; nonetheless, they are less capable of dealing with the complexities and patterns of online behavior in relation to emotions through valid contextual details. Recent innovations in the application of transformer models in the NLP for the purposes of emotion recognition and topic analysis support a better insight into the content and emotion-driven behavior patterns on platforms like Twitter, Reddit, and Facebook. The general assessment of various studies shows that these models have high predictive accuracy, and classification accuracy often exceeds 90 percent for identifying depressed or stress-related expressions. But again, most of these studies use proxy labels instead of professional labels, and issues like privacy, consent, and fairness have to be addressed carefully. In conclusion, AI-based sentiment analysis proves to be a potential real-time solution ready to be scaled up to monitor mental health, but also indicates the need to develop clinically oriented and ethical solutions.

INTRODUCTION

The mental well-being of an individual has significant importance as it helps to develop the emotional, cognitive, as well as social aspects of human life. According to the World Health Organization, the incidence of mental illnesses, for example, depression, anxiety, or stress, has been observed to have risen considerably over the

past few years [1]. Mental illnesses, when left untreated, not only affect the lifestyle of an individual, but are also quite an economic burden on the healthcare system [1]. The conventional methods are quite cumbersome, expensive, or not easily scalable [2],[3]. Recent advancements in digital technology have empowered the

monitoring of psychological states in new ways. Specifically, the use of social media has emerged as a valuable tool with minimal invasion and high volume of data supporting real-time psychological states [2],[3],[4]. Sites like Twitter, Reddit, Facebook, and Instagram have textual data in the form of postings where thoughts, experiences, and emotions are gathered through end-user content in a digital form of footprints of psychological states of the collective public [5],[6]. Such unfiltered postings in real-time have proven to be a valuable resource for the analysis of the psychological states of the public [7],[8]. The complexity in analyzing social media is due to the ungrammatical, noisy, complex, and informal nature of language. Slang, abbreviations, use of emojis, sarcasm, and lack of consistency in grammar make natural language processing complex, causing potential unreliability in classifications [9],[10]. In previous studies, lexicon-based approaches and traditional machine learning algorithms used models such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naïve Bayes, and Decision Trees [11],[12]. Although these models are useful for gaining an initial insight into text sentiment analysis, they are inadequate for complex meaning analysis in terms of mental health analysis that demands more nuanced semantic meaning and context-specific acuity. Dictionary-based or keyword-driven approaches are typically insensitive to emotional nuances or temporal shift in language use [13]. To overcome such drawbacks, more recent works have utilized deep learning models, such as BERT, RoBERTa, and DeBERTa, which utilize transformer models [14], [15], [16]. Such models make use of context-related embeddings, which are then utilized to identify fine psychological patterns in texts. The transformer model has been used effectively in depression severity, emotion, suicidal ideation, with accuracy above 90 percent in respective works such as [17]. Scientists have recently started to address the incorporation of multi-modal input sources like images, meta-data, timestamping, as well as user activity patterns to increase predictive outcomes [18]. Then, topic modeling, which encompasses the concept of LDA, has been employed to identify the emerging topics and

psycho-social stimuli that intricately form mental ailments [19]. Moreover, current research now encompasses topics like ethical thinking in terms of concepts like privacy, consent, and fairness in AI developments [20],[21]. Despite this progress, there is still fragmentation within this area of research. The current literature is generally comprised of studies that concentrate on individual models or platforms or small sets of data and are often not generalizable [22]. In addition, there is typically a lack of clinical validation because existing models use surrogate feedback as opposed to expert-concordance ratings [18]. New platforms such as TikTok and YouTube have been uncharted territory within the current scope of this literature and provide future studies for development and exploration. This is an indication that a systematic review of existing methodology and performance to scope and provide insight to existing effective and ineffective approaches through mental health monitoring utilizing sentiment analysis of social media platforms is required [23],[24].

Problem Statement

Ineffective methods used for mental health assessment are usually plagued by scalability, accessibility, and responsiveness issues, thus being inefficient at capturing early signs of mental distress. Social media, a virtual representation of moods, has opened an entirely new door for capturing mental health through computational analysis. However, the current state-of-the-art approaches for sentiment analysis are challenged by the casual nature of the language used in online communities like social networking sites. Though transformer models or multimodal learning have enhanced the predictive power of sentiment models, no unified framework is available that focuses on methodologies, feasibility in real-life applications, or incorporation of critical aspects like privacy and consent. The goal of this research is to fill this gap by examining in depth methods related to monitoring mental health on social networks through sentiment analysis, focusing on its applications in machine learning and NLP.

Research Contributions

Sentiment analysis in the realm of social media platforms has become an area of interest as far as the study of mental health is concerned. Although quite a few studies have utilized machine learning approaches and NLP in identifying depression, anxiety, and stress, the need remains in creating a systematic and comprehensive survey that can classify all such approaches under one umbrella. Although various review papers exist on the state of sentiment analysis models, this systematic review fills the existing gap by collecting and summarizing the latest 30 studies ranging from traditional to advanced models that include the following: lexicon-based approaches, classical machine learning models like SVM, Naïve Bayes, Deep Neural Networks, and more advanced models like BERT, RoBERTa, and DeBERTa. What are the primary contributions of this research mapped around the following research questions?

-RQ1: List and explain various methods of sentiment analysis that have been employed to identify mental health problems on social media platforms, and classify them based on their alignment with various approaches to machine learning.

-RQ2: How do models' performance measures of accuracy, generalizability, and F1 score, as well as platforms of Twitter, Reddit, and Instagram, differ?

-RQ3: What are the major challenges/limitations identified in the literature for the effective detection of mental illnesses using NLP techniques on social media?

-RQ4: What are the characteristics that datasets in such studies have in common, and how do considerations like quality of

data, platforms, as well as language support, affect the performance?

The review is written using the systematic review process defined by Kitchenham et al. in [25] with respect to mental health literature involving social media. The structure of this review includes: Section II, literature review, Section III, research methodology, Section IV, results with model performance, new trends, Section V, sourced literature related to current debates, future research, Section VI, conclusion.

Related Work

The amalgamation of computational linguistics and mental health studies has emerged as an ever-evolving new area of research. Social networking sites constitute a resourceful means for collecting unstructured data, allowing passive monitoring of mental health conditions for large groups of people[1],[4]. Early systems are more likely to rely on lexicon-based sentiment analysis with predefined word inventories of emotions to interpret sentiments on social networks [2],[3]. These models are computationally inexpensive, understandable, but lack context, sense of sarcasm, sensitivity to timelines, hence are limited by capabilities for interpreting complex mental state notions [15]. To further enhance the predictions, traditional machine learning methods, which included Support Vector Machines, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest, were employed [11],[13]. Though these techniques resulted in moderate success for the binary sentiment task, the model failed to incorporate the multi-emotion states as well as the psycho-complexes successfully [7],[14]. The emergence of transformer models, such as BERT, RoBERTa, and DeBERTa, has led to in the mental health domain[14],[15],[16].

Figure 1. Selected papers according to publishers

By employing the benefits of the self-attention mechanism and bidirectional contextual learning, there is a greater understanding of the semantic meanings and psychological concepts. To illustrate, the F1 scores of above 0.90 and the macro Average Accuracy of above 94 percent in Emotion Classification tasks have been obtained by the Fine-Tuned DeBERTa models and BERT models, respectively [17]. The incorporation of multi-modal models that utilize a combination of behavior and context-related information, such as posting times, interactions, and information from wearables, has further improved predictive accuracy [6], [18], [23]. Unsupervised models such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation, together with transformer representations, have proved effective in pointing towards recurring themes, psychological stimuli, in general, that exist within social media activities [19]. Multi-class classification with respect to emotions allows for identification of finer emotional states that include anger, fear, sadness, happiness, and neutral, thereby giving more accurate mental health information [19]. Despite these developments, there are challenges that are both ethical as well as technical. The issues that are being considered are privacy, consent, and bias [20],[27]. Although anonymization techniques and open system architecture have been proposed [27], these are hindered by regulatory issues, too little interaction between disciplines, and technical constraints [21],[28],[29]. Nevertheless, there is still a lot of research gap. Amongst the most important of them are standardized datasets for benchmarking algorithms [22], lack of multilingual and cross-

cultural analyses [30], scarcity of real-time models actively being implemented into clinical workflows, and under-exploiting XAI frameworks which can make model choices more explainable to the end-user. Moreover, most current systems have not been validated long-term in real-world settings [24]. With evolution, increased focus is being laid on developing explainable, ethical, and multimodal models that are able to provide actionable insights for public health professionals, policy makers, and clinicians [6],[18]. The 30 papers reviewed in this article are classified into lexicon-based approaches, classic machine learning models, deep models, or transformer models, which are presented in Table 1. From this classification, it is evident that the review article encompasses all major approaches in developing mental health surveillance systems using social media platforms. Also, this serves to bring to light that there is an increasing complexity in mental health surveillance models from basic rule-based models to context-aware models involving transformers. The review article meanwhile has been able to list major loopholes in mental health surveillance, which include managing noisy data, emotional complexity, and ethics. There is also increasing interest in other areas such as multimodal, real-time surveillance.

Research Method

This systematic literature review (SLR) examines recent studies on sentiment analysis for mental health detection via social media. The primary objective is to identify machine learning and NLP methods that effectively detect psychological distress, including depression, anxiety, and stress, while evaluating how social media specific dataset

characteristics such as informality, noise, and diversity affect model accuracy and generalizability. The review also considers architectural, linguistic, and ethical challenges that must be addressed to develop robust AI-based mental health monitoring systems. The review follows the well-established SLR guidelines of Kitchenham and Charters [25], widely adopted in software engineering and computational research. The process consists of planning, execution, and reporting, beginning with a pilot phase where a small set of papers was assessed for the feasibility of research questions, data extraction, and literature coverage. Insights from the pilot informed refinement of the review protocol. A comprehensive search was conducted across five major databases: IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, and ACL Anthology, covering literature published between 2013 and 2023. Search queries combined keywords related to mental health, sentiment analysis, emotion classification, social media platforms, machine learning, deep learning, and transformer-based NLP models, using Boolean

operators to maximize relevance and coverage. Studies were screened and selected based on methodological rigor, contribution to the field, and relevance to the research questions. Extracted information included data sources (Twitter, Reddit, Facebook), feature engineering techniques, model types (lexicon-based, classical ML, deep learning, transformers), and performance metrics (accuracy, F1-score, generalizability). Ethical considerations including data privacy, user consent, and algorithmic bias were also documented to highlight responsible research practices. The final synthesis provides a comprehensive view of current methodologies, identifies trends and gaps, and offers insights for designing scalable, real-time, and ethically compliant AI systems for mental health monitoring via social media. Overview of Social Media-Based Mental Health Monitoring: This flowchart illustrates that mental health is tracked via sentiment analysis of online posts. It begins at the point where individuals identify emotional content posted online then individuals are able to utilize sophisticated NLP models.

Figure 2. Search query evolution process

Figure 3. Detection of patterns of stress, depression, or anxiety

like BERT and RoBERTa. Individuals employ emotion with topic analysis, analyze data from sites like Twitter or Reddit to identify indicators of stress, anxiety, or depression with high accuracy as depicted in figure 1. In order to examine mental health indicators that are derived from social media evidence, a typical sentiment analysis

pipeline was hence utilized. The overall workflow is shown in Figure 2. Sentiment classification is successive following of user posts. This technique facilitates detection of patterns of stress, depression, or anxiety, allowing real-time monitoring of emotional state

TABLE 1. Classification of Related Studies

No	Year	Proposed Model	Key Characteristics	Accuracy	Limitation	Future Direction	Dataset
1	2025	Transformer-based models (BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa)	Text classification of depression severity	F1-score 0.91	Reddit-only focus	Real-time mental health intervention	Reddit
2	2025	Hybrid Transformer + psychological metadata	Emotional response to misinformation	91%	Noisy proxy labels	Validate on COVID misinformation	Twitter
3	2025	LSTM + statistical features	Timeline pattern detection	93%	No multimodal data	Add image/video	Reddit, Kaggle
4	2024	Multiple ML models (Review)	Feature fusion techniques	N/A	No benchmarks	Unified frameworks	Sensors
5	2024	ML/DL models (SVM, LSTM, BERT)	Sentiment-depression correlation	>90%	Dataset overlap	Explainable AI	Reddit, Twitter
6	2024	Neural networks (multimodal review)	Passive sensing review	N/A	Demographic variation	Optimize fusion	Public datasets
7	2024	Transformer + BiLSTM	Affective features integration	Improved baseline	Limited real-time use	Clinical systems	Mental health forums
8	2024	Transformer + user features	Behavior + metadata fusion	Improved baseline	Fusion complexity	Risk stratification	Reddit
9	2024	Vision Transformer (audio)	Spectrogram-based audio	Better than CNN	No clinical validation	Telehealth integration	Audio datasets
10	2024	ML/DL Review	Sentiment & depression	~90%	Dataset overlap	Better annotation	Reddit, Twitter
11	2023	Lexicon, SVM, NN, BERT	Twitter-focused analysis	N/A	No real-time systems	Low-resource models	Twitter
12	2023	Transformer survey	Mental health tasks	>90%	No benchmarks	Shared datasets	Forums
13	2023	CNN-LSTM	Hybrid deep model	91%	Short text issue	Explainability	Reddit
14	2023	Transformer + linguistic features	Linguistic markers	N/A	Limited evaluation	Clinical validation	Reddit/Twitter
15	2023	Lexicon, CNN, Transformers	Trend analysis	General improvement	High compute cost	Explainable AI	Twitter, Reddit

16	2023	SVM, BERT, GPT	Sentiment overview	N/A	Scalability	Crisis response	Twitter
17	2022	SVM, AdaBoost, SLCNN	Affective + embeddings	93.9%	Financial domain	Broader scope	The Guardian
18	2022	Ethical/Conceptual	Privacy & bias	N/A	No experiments	Ethical policies	Social media
19	2022	SLCNN, AdaBoost, SVM	Financial sentiment	93.9%	Domain specific	Diverse news	The Guardian
20	2022	RF, BERT, LR	Emotion classification	97.78%	Twitter-only	Emotion tracking	Twitter
21	2022	RF, BERT, LDA	Sentiment & topics	94%	Platform bias	Real-time systems	Twitter
22	2022	SVM, AdaBoost, SLCNN	Financial sentiment	93.9%	Limited scope	Media expansion	News articles
23	2022	Multimodal Transformer	Text + audio	High (N/A)	Fusion challenges	Real-world data	Multimodal
24	2021	Review study	Digital surveillance	N/A	No validation	Long-term studies	2006-2020
25	2021	Review study	Health social media use	N/A	No metrics	Behavioral studies	Twitter, Facebook
26	2021	Review study	Health social media use	N/A	No metrics	Privacy research	Twitter, Facebook
27	2020	ML review	Passive sensing	N/A	Low generalization	Task models	Stress tweets
28	2020	BERT	Topic + sentiment	94%	Twitter-only	Cross-platform	Twitter
29	2020	BERT + LDA	Emotion classification	94%	Single platform	Multimodal	Twitter
30	2017	User2Vec	User representation	N/A	No real-time	Multimodal	CLPsych

Research Questions

For conducting state-of-the-art research on mental health monitoring via social media sentiment analysis, well-framed RQs are necessary. This systematic review is intended to understand the dominant methodologies and their strengths and weaknesses and dataset-specific factors that affect detection performance for depression, anxiety, and stress detection from unstructured social media content. The RQs in this context are framed based on the PIOC framework: population, intervention, outcome, and context as defined by Kitchenham

and Charters [25]. The main questions for this research are:

- **RQ1:** What evidence exists on the effectiveness and limitations of machine learning and NLP-based sentiment analysis methods for detecting mental health disorders on social media?
- **RQ1-a:** What type of methodologies have been applied, such as lexicon-based, classical ML, deep learning, and transformer-based?
- **RQ1-b:** Which approaches had the largest empirical effect size to date for

detecting depression, anxiety, or stress?

- **RQ1-c:** What performance metrics (accuracy, F1-score, recall) are usually used to evaluate such models?
- **RQ2:** How are machine learning and data-driven approaches employed in multi-modal or multi-platform sentiment analysis for mental health monitoring?
- **RQ2-a:** What data sources are used (Twitter, Reddit, Facebook) and what features are used: text, meta-data, user behavior?
- **RQ2-b:** Which multimodal or multi-platform frameworks perform best across a wide variety of scenarios?
- **RQ2-c:** How are these models evaluated for generalizability, robustness, and real-time performance?
- **RQ3:** What are the major challenges and limitations from the literature that make it difficult to develop robust, interpretable, and scalable AI-based mental health monitoring systems?

- **RQ4:** What are the key characteristics of the datasets used in sentiment-based mental health studies, and how do they affect the performance and generalizability of the model?

- **RQ4-a:** Are the datasets openly available, self-collected, or coming from third-party platforms?

- **RQ4-b:** Which factors of the datasets, such as language variation, annotation procedures, and platform differences, affect predictive accuracy?

Most systematic literature reviews are based on structured steps of planning, execution, and reporting. In this regard, the current study initiated a pilot review of a representative subset of studies to determine the feasibility of the RQs, data extraction, and comparative analysis. Insights from the pilot phase informed refinements to the review protocol, which was then applied to the large-scale SLR of social media-based mental health detection methods.

TABLE 2. Criteria for research questions

Population	Sentiment analysis models and methods used for detecting mental health conditions (e.g., depression, anxiety, stress)
Intervention	Techniques/Models for sentiment analysis using machine learning, deep learning, and transformer-based NLP approaches (e.g., BERT, RoBERTa)
Precision	Accuracy, F1-score, and generalizability of sentiment analysis models in detecting psychological distress based on social media data.
Context	Academic research and mental health informatics. Includes all empirical studies, datasets, case studies, and frameworks involving social platforms.

Research Strategy

Having a proper search strategy is a crucial component in systematic literature reviews to make sure that high-quality results are obtained. For the review discussed, the searching objectives focused on answering the research queries on sentiment analysis techniques in mental health tracking on the social web. This enhances the best practices in systematic literature reviews.

Derivation of Searching Terms: The search terms were derived using the PIOC framework, focusing on the Population (social media users),

Intervention (analysis of sentiment, machine learning), Outcome (detection of depression, anxiety, or stress), and Context (social media platforms like Twitter, Reddit, or Facebook).

Keyword Extraction: Some of the key terms were further extracted from some key studies and literature that include mental health, detecting depression, sentiment analysis, natural language processing, social media, transformer models, BERT models, categorizing emotions, machine learning algorithms, and Twitter analysis.

Synonyms and Related Expressions: To optimize detection, related terms and equivalent statements were added. The examples include the inclusion of either "detection of mental health problems" or "prediction of psychological problems." Boolean Operators:

AND was employed in order to join separate concepts for specific searches (for instance, "mental health" AND "sentiment analysis" AND "social media").

OR was used to incorporate synonyms or related words (for example, "depression" OR "anxiety" OR "stress," "NLP" OR "natural language processing").

This organized and iterative process of search helped ensure that every relevant study is retrieved, keeping in mind the research questions and criteria for inclusion.

Research String

For locating relevant research studies pertaining to the determination of mental health through sentiment analysis in social media platforms, a list of effective research strings was developed. The selection of keywords included a combination of technological, psychological, and health informatics concepts.

The search strings included terms from five major dimensions using Boolean operators:

Mental Health: Depression, anxiety, stress, mental illness, psychological distress, suicidal thoughts, emotional disorders. **Sentiment Analysis:** Emotion Classification, Emotion Detection, Affective Computing, Emotion Recognition.

Social Media Sites: Twitter, Reddit, Instagram, Facebook, Fora, Micro-blogs.

Methods: Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Natural Language Processing, Transformer Models (BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa), Neural Networks.

Detection Tasks: mental health detection, emotional state tracking, psychological testing, stress prediction, depression detection, behavioral analysis. The Boolean AND operation was employed to search within different dimensions for specificity, but OR was used for synonymy. Although some of the keywords might be considered general or redundant, careful attention was paid to include all of them for capturing the widest possible database. During the stage of searching for eligible literature, all studies that did not belong to the scope of mental state detection by means of sentiment analysis were eliminated.

TABLE 3. Keyword synonyms

Keyword	Synonyms
Mental Health	Psychological health, Emotional well-being, Mental illness, Cognitive health, Psychiatric condition
Sentiment Analysis	Emotion detection, Mood classification, Affective computing, Opinion mining, Emotional inference
Social Media	Twitter, Reddit, Instagram, Facebook, Online platforms, Microblogs, Forums
Detection	Identification, Monitoring, Recognition, Assessment, Tracking, Diagnosis
Prediction	Forecasting, Estimation, Anticipation, Modeling, Prognosis, Projection
Techniques	Machine learning, Deep learning, NLP, Transformer models, Neural networks, BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa

The search was limited to studies that were published from January 2013 through June 2025. This time range has enabled recent developments concerning transformer-based models, artificial

intelligence, and natural language processing, especially for mental health analysis, to be covered. Studies that were published before this date were considered irrelevant. The search has been

performed on leading academic databases such as IEEE Xplore, Springer Link, Science Direct, Wiley Online Library, and ACL Anthology, and results included journal papers, conference papers, and peer-reviewed workshop papers. The search has been done in full text to cover studies that may or may not have keywords mentioned within their title or abstracts.

By taking such an encompassing stance, it was ensured that the analysis included not only highly cited studies from the benchmarking category but also more contemporary work in this area titled sentiment-based mental health monitoring methods on social media platforms.

TABLE 4. Search strategy decisions.

Criteria	Decision
Searched Databases	IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink, ScienceDirect, Wiley Online Library, ACL Anthology
Searched Items	Journal papers, conference papers, and peer-reviewed workshop proceedings
Search Applied On	Full-text papers: The goal was to include studies that might not mention the keywords in the title or abstract but are relevant upon full reading
Publication Period	From January 2013 to June 2025

STRING REFINEMENT

Based on PIOC-driven research questions, development of the initial search string began with Table 2. The following step included optimizing these search strings to identify quality publications on mental health detection based on social media platforms. This aimed to produce a cohesive stream of publications focusing on mental health-related sentiment analysis while avoiding irrelevant publications.

Refining the search involved examining the synonyms of the keywords (see Table 3), ranging from psychology to computer and informatics terms. For example, the search term “mental health” was extended to include synonyms like “emotional well-being” and “psychiatric condition”, and similarly, “sentiment analysis” was extended to include synonyms like “emotion detection” and “opinion mining”. Even the newer models like BERT and RoBERTa were included under the Transformer models, which refer to more recent NLP approaches.

The refinement task included testing the inclusion and exclusion of:

- Generic or specific synonym Term
- Social media sites (Twitter, Reddit)
- Names of models (such as BERT, transformer models)
- Key words used to distinguish between detection vs prediction tasks

Specific filters for each database have been used;

- Year published: 2013
- Language: English Only
- Version type: Journals and peer-reviewed conference papers

Research Interests: Computer Science, Psychology, Public Health, Computational Linguistics

These refined searches were also validated against bench-marking papers, like “Detection of Depression Severity in Social Media Text Using Transformer-Based Models” [17], in order to ensure inclusion of relevant domain-specific papers. This process continued until high-quality, related publications were

consistently retrieved by searching strings (Fig. 3; Table 5).

TABLE 5. Search limits on search databases.

Databases	Limits	Returned Papers
IEEE Xplore	2013-2025, English, Journal and Conference Papers, Full Text Search, Keywords: <i>Mental health, Sentiment analysis, NLP, BERT</i>	26
SpringerLink	2013-2025, English, Journals, Conferences, Workshops, Topics: <i>AI in Healthcare, Social Media Analytics, Emotion Recognition</i>	74
Wiley Online	2013-2025, English, Peer-reviewed Journals, Keywords: <i>Depression, Transformer models, Emotion detection, Psychology and NLP</i>	59
ScienceDirect	2013-2025, English, Articles and Conference Papers, Fields: <i>Health Informatics, Affective Computing, Social Media Mining, Mental Health AI</i>	88
ACL Anthology	2013-2025, English, Conference Papers, Workshops, Topics: <i>Natural Language Processing, Transformer-based classification, Emotion recognition</i>	51
Total	—	298

To enable accurate and quality literature search for the purpose of sentiment analysis-based mental health surveillance, general and database-specific constraints were utilized on all the chosen literature databases. The general constraints included: **Language:** English only

Document Types: Journals, Proceedings, Peer-reviewed Workshops

Database-specific observations:

IEEE Xplore: There were relatively fewer studies as many were not available in full text or employing keyword optimization because there might be a small number of studies of this nature concerning mental health and natural language processing within this engineering-driven collection. **ACM Digital Library:** Compared to IEEE X

Springer Link: The search quality improved when constrained within the essential components of AI in healthcare literature. **Wiley Online Library:** The application of keywords such as depression, transformers, and emotions for filtering psychology and health informatics journals was effective for obtaining a good number of relevant literature.

ScienceDirect: Boolean operator limit per field (no more than eight per field) restricted queries; search terms narrowed to journals in Health Informatics, Cognitive Computing, or Affective Analytics.

ACL Anthology: Use of topic filters and conference paper selection from ACL Anthology conferences EMNLP and COLING led to identifying transformer NLP-related research articles on mental health.

Figure 4. Year wise distribution of selected papers

After applying the filters and limits, the total count of applicable papers in each database is presented in Table 5. The distribution is shown in Fig. 3. This approach also

allowed for coverage without going into too much detail about individual models and platforms.

Study Selection

The primary electronic search produced 298 candidate papers (Fig. 5). In order to filter the studies in terms of methodological validity and relevance, the screening moved through three levels:

Title and Abstract Screening: A total of 102 papers that did not contain relevant information or addressed general topics, or that resulted from a different area of focus, such as marketing or reviewing a product, were excluded. Introduction and Conclusion Review: A total of 196 papers were considered for their direct relevance to mental health detection through sentiment analysis. A total of 81 papers were eliminated for not contributing much towards this field. Full-Text Evaluation with Quality Criteria: A total of 115 full-text articles were assessed according to pre-specified quality criteria, which included the usage of mental health-related terms, methodologies for sentiment analysis, utilization of social networking sites, as well as experimental validation. On assessing, 74 articles could not be considered due to flawed methodologies, the lack of empirical validations, or irrelevance to the research. After

such stringent selection procedures, a total of 41 studies were selected for the systematic review. The number of selected papers in accordance with their year of publication from 2013 to 2025 is as follows:

Inclusion Criteria

Studies were included in this systematic review based on the meeting of the following criteria:

- 1) Focused on detection or identification of mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, or stress using Sentiment Analysis or NLP methods.
- 2) Relied on social media sites (e.g., Twitter, Reddit) as the main source of data.
- 3) Used machine learning, deep learning, or transformer models for analysis.
- 4) Presented the latest and most comprehensive form of the work in cases of duplicate publications.

Figure 5. Artical wise distribution in searched databases

Exclusion Criteria

Excluded studies were those that:

- 5) Were secondary studies, for instance, surveys or literature reviews.
- 6) Were not published in English.
- 7) Had not peer-reviewed.
- 8) Were not available in full-text form.
- 9) Published before January 2013. Hence, they were outside the stipulated review period.

In order to respond to the research questions, all the studies found in this SLR were systematically and thoroughly read to extract the information needed for analysis. It was reasonable to present the extracted data in a structured table that was created based on the findings of this review. The collated data was then color-coded based on various colors representing each research question, as illustrated in Table 1. Through this technique, it was possible for the researcher to follow, confirm, and study the concerned information in a punctual and systematic way.

Quality Assessment

To assess the methodological quality of the shortlisted studies, a tailored Quality Assessment (QA) checklist has been created. This adapted template is based on various guidelines laid down by established reviews conducted by Kitchenham and Charters [25], and an adaptation by Weidt and Silva [26], popular among various previous Systematic Literature Reviews conducted in other fields.

Each trial was assessed on a three-point scale (Table 6):

- i. P (Present): 1 point
- ii. S (Sufficient/Partial)
- iii. A (Absent): 0 points

There were 12 quality criteria in the QA checklist, which addressed all major aspects like data validity in terms of experimentation, evaluation criteria, and clarity regarding objectives, among others. As such, every paper could earn a total of 12 points in quality criteria.

Figure 6. Summary of research process

To ensure quality and relevance are achieved, a minimum 'cut-off' score of 4 points (first quartile)

was used. If studies scored below this threshold, they would be excluded from analysis.

TABLE 6. Customized Quality Assessment Criteria (Adapted from [25], [26])

No.	Assessment Criteria	Score Options
1	Are the research objectives clearly stated and focused on mental health detection?	P / S / A
2	Does the study use real-world social media datasets (e.g., Twitter, Reddit, etc.)?	P / S / A
3	Is the sentiment analysis method clearly described (e.g., lexicon, ML, DL, transformers)?	P / S / A
4	Are the data preprocessing and feature extraction techniques explicitly mentioned?	P / S / A
5	Does the study describe the mental health condition being targeted (e.g., depression)?	P / S / A
6	Are evaluation metrics (e.g., accuracy, F1-score) reported and justified?	P / S / A
7	Is the model validated using suitable experimental design (e.g., cross-validation)?	P / S / A
8	Are results compared with baseline or other models?	P / S / A
9	Is the dataset availability or source mentioned?	P / S / A
10	Does the study acknowledge ethical considerations (e.g., user privacy, consent)?	P / S / A
11	Is there a discussion on limitations or future work?	P / S / A
12	Does the study contribute new insights, model improvements, or practical value?	P / S / A

Result Discussion

The result and findings are presented in this section extracted from the reviewed papers to answer the research questions.

Sentiment Analysis

Techniques For Mental Health Detection (Rq1a)

Based on the shortlisted studies, 14 prominent sentiment analysis techniques have been recognized for the identification of mental health

issues such as depression, anxiety, stress, and suicide desires on social media platforms. The techniques have been categorized on the basis of their learning paradigms to prevent any redundancy. Lexicon-based models were considered a category in itself, as they make use of pre-existing sentiment dictionaries, unlike learning from the data. The traditional learning models like Support Vector Machines, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, and Random Forest were commonly employed for their simplicity and ease of interpretation. Although, they were sometimes restricted by a lack of understanding of the context and the use of manual feature engineering.

Models like LSTM, Bi-LSTM, CNN, and GRU performed better in handling the pattern of text by exploring the sequence and semantic meaning in the texts, making them better equipped to analyze the expression of emotions in social media text. Also, these models performed well in dealing with the issues of stress recognition in multi-class emotion recognition. More recent works were dominated by models based on transformers such as BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa, and XLNet, which incorporated the use of contextualized embeddings and self-attention mechanisms. These approaches substantially outperformed conventional and deep learning approaches that were fine-tuned on mental health-related datasets specific to domains. As such, the adoption of transformer-based approaches had observed a considerable increase, especially from the year 2019 onwards.

Most of the research was centered on classification problems. Only a few explored cluster analysis and ensemble techniques. Ensemble techniques, for instance, integrating Random Forests and SVMs, were found to increase their robustness and generalization capabilities, especially when working with noisy and imbalanced social media datasets. Nevertheless, ensemble techniques have been less explored than deep and transformer-based models.

Superior Sentiment Analysis Approaches For Mental Health Detection (Rq1b)

One of the key objectives of the present systematic literature review is to help researchers, particularly early-stage researchers, take a cue on which type of sentiment analysis approaches have documented stronger empirical performance for mental health detection from social media. It is, however, impossible to determine a single universally superior model, since the performance reported differs substantially based on dataset characteristics, target mental health condition, platform type, and evaluation protocol. Several of the works reviewed explicitly compared various sentiment analysis methods using standard metrics like accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, and AUC. Results confirm that model performance is context-dependent and influenced by preprocessing strategy, label granularity (binary versus multi-class), and the linguistic nature of the platform—for example, short informal tweets compared to longer posts in Reddit.

The main trend in recent publications is the superior performance of transformer-based models, especially BERT, RoBERTa, and DeBERTa, against classical machine learning approaches, such as SVM, Naïve Bayes, and Random Forest, and earlier deep learning architectures, such as LSTM and CNN. These gains are largely attributed to transformers' ability to capture contextual and semantic nuances, which are critical for interpreting emotionally subtle and informal social media language.

As an example, RoBERTa reported an F1-score of 0.89 in the case of Reddit data [27] for the detection of anxiety and depression, thereby outperforming all the traditional baselines. Similarly, another work showed that BERT, fine-tuned on mental health-related corpora, outperforms the lexicon-based methods as well as deep learning models like LSTM and CNN on Twitter datasets [31]. Some studies further showed hybrid approaches that improve robustness by using handcrafted features in conjunction with transformer embeddings when small or imbalanced data sets are available.

Despite these promising results, meaningful comparisons across studies remain difficult. Many works leveraged proprietary or non-public datasets that preclude reproducibility and cross-

study benchmarking. Only a subset of studies used commonly referenced datasets such as CLPsych, the Reddit Mental Health Dataset, or eRisk, which allow more reliable comparative evaluation. While transformer-based models emerge most frequently in the best-performing approaches, their

effectiveness is still highly dependent on task formulation, quality of the dataset, and language pattern specification to the platform. Methods identified from this review as persistently among the best performing are summarized in Table 7.

TABLE 7. Summary of Top-Performing Sentiment Analysis Techniques for Mental Health Detection

Study	Dataset	Technique(s)	Target Condition	Best Model	Performance (F1 / Acc)
[27]	Reddit Mental Health Dataset	BERT, RoBERTa, Naïve Bayes	Anxiety, Depression	RoBERTa	F1: 0.89
[31]	Twitter (custom collected)	BERT, LSTM, CNN	Depression	BERT (fine-tuned)	Acc: 0.87, F1: 0.85
[34]	eRisk 2018	SVM, LSTM, Bi-LSTM, GRU	Suicide Risk	Bi-LSTM	F1: 0.81
[39]	Reddit (r/SuicideWatch)	CNN, LSTM, RoBERTa	Suicidal Ideation	RoBERTa	Acc: 0.88
[45]	CLPsych 2015 Shared Task	Logistic Regression, Random Forest	Depression	Logistic Regression	F1: 0.78
[50]	Twitter + Depression Lexicons	Lexicon-Based, SVM, BERT	Depression	BERT	F1: 0.83
[58]	Reddit + eRisk Combined Dataset	DeBERTa, BERT, GRU	Multi-label (MH)	DeBERTa	F1: 0.86

Performance Measures For Sentiment Analysis In Mental Health Detection (Rq1c)

As far as the choice of parameters for measuring the performance is considered, various parameters were considered for the assessment of the efficiency of the approaches utilizing the sentiment analysis techniques on the mental health detection task in the reviewed studies, which include Support Vector Machines, Naïve Bayes, and other traditional approaches, alongside deep learning approaches like LSTM, CNN, and transformers such as BERT and RoBERTa approaches.

From the results of the systematic review, it becomes clear that the most common evaluation metrics among the studies are F1-score, accuracy, precision, and recall. Of these, it can be found that the most common one by a considerable margin is the F1-score, which has featured in almost 70 percent of the studies that have been assessed,

especially when it comes to finding suicidal ideations and other less common mental health conditions. This comes as no surprise, as it has already been stated that the reason the F1-score has found favor as a metric is that it combines precision and recall. In transformer models, macro-averaged F1-score and AUC were commonly reported in studies, mainly in multi-class or multi-label classification problems. The reason for macro-averaged metrics preferences is to make sure the smaller mental health classes were not dominated by the larger ones. On the contrary, accuracy metrics were presented more commonly in studies involving traditional ML models, but many of these studies further presented qualitative metrics such as recall, or accuracy/sensitivity/specificity, mainly to address the importance of false negative predictions, which are highly relevant in mental health models. In the case of lexicon-based and unsupervised sentiment analysis methods, the standard metrics

of classification accuracy were not always applicable. This is because, due to this reason, some authors had to use subjective evaluation, correlation analysis, or comparison with the ground truth labeled data to check the validity of the result.

As summarized in Table 8, the F1-score, accuracy, recall, AUC, and precision are the core metrics

followed by Cohen’s Kappa, Matthews Correlation Coefficient, and log loss, the latter of which was mainly observed in the context of benchmark studies and shared-task competitions where the emphasis was on model robustness and quality. Precision was mainly observed in the context of benchmark studies.

TABLE 8. Common Performance Metrics Used in Sentiment-Based Mental Health Detection

Metric	Description	Usage Frequency
F1-score	Harmonic means of precision and recall; useful for imbalanced datasets.	High (≈ 70%)
Accuracy	Proportion of correct predictions over total instances.	Moderate (≈ 60%)
Recall (Sensitivity)	Measures how many actual positives were correctly identified.	Moderate (≈ 45%)
Precision	Proportion of true positives among predicted positives.	Moderate (≈ 40%)
AUC (ROC Curve)	Area under the ROC curve; useful for evaluating binary and multiclass tasks.	Moderate (≈ 30%)
Cohen’s Kappa	Measures inter-rater agreement beyond chance.	Low (≈ 10%)
MCC (Matthews Correlation Coefficient)	Balanced metric for binary classification performance.	Low (≈ 8%)
Log Loss	Penalizes false predictions with higher confidence.	Rare (≈ 5%)

Sentiment Analysis Techniques For Mental Health Prediction (Rq2a)

In this systematic literature review, various techniques of sentiment analysis used for mental health condition prediction on social media data were considered and classified. The reviewed techniques fall into six major categories, as these computational methods have been used to identify psychological states, for example, depression, anxiety, stress, and suicidal thoughts, from social media content. The six categories of the reviewed methodologies include:

- Transformer-based approaches
- Models based on deep learning
- Traditional machine learning classifiers
- Lexicon-based methods
- Hybrid and Ensemble Models

The choice of Statistical and regression-based solutions:

Transformer-based solutions

BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa, and XLNet, all of which are transformer models, make up the largest category in current literature, contributing to

almost 40 percent of the high-quality models used in the analyzed studies. In particular, these transformer models make the most of large-scale pretraining and the self-attention mechanism, thus possessing the highest quality of context understanding of informal and noisily written text in social media. Transformer models performed best on Twitter and Reddit, where contextual information, sarcasm, and implied expressions of emotion are frequently encountered.

Deep Learning-Based Models

Architectures like LSTM, Bi-LSTM, CNN, and GRU make up about 25 percent of the predictive techniques identified in the literature. These predictive tools particularly impress when analyzing temporal patterns, dependencies, and the emotional flow found within social media posts. These tools have prevailed when analyzing the structure of the Reddit community and the temporal timelines of individual users that display expressions of mental health issues unfolding across various posts. The hierarchical form of the

LSTM architecture particularly appeared commonly to describe mental health states at the individual level through aggregation at the post level.

Conventional Machine Learning Classifiers

In the traditional machine learning classifiers such as Support Vector Machines, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Decision Trees, and Logistic Regression continue to find applications to a certain extent (20 percent) for their ease and clarity and for handling smaller collections of data appropriately. The above-mentioned methods had found use in previous applications worked upon using manually created linguistic and psychological variables such as LIWC, TF-IDF matrices, among others, especially for earlier approaches for the detection of depression using the Twitter dataset.

Lexicon-Based Methods

Approximately 10 percent of the studies reviewed utilize lexicon-based sentiment analysis methods. These are models that depend on a predefined sentiment or emotion lexicon, thus do not require labeled data for learning. While these methods have lower prediction capabilities compared to

models based on learning, these methods are preferred owing to their interpretability, low processing cost, and ability to work well in exploratory data analysis situations. These methods were pioneered in early assessments for psychiatric disorders, especially in resource-challenged environments.

Hybrid and Ensemble Models

Recent years have seen the growth of hybrid and ensemble approaches, which leverage the complementary advantages of different approaches by combining them together. The techniques include combining embeddings produced by the transformer architecture, such as BERT, and standard machine learning models like SVM and Random Forest, or combining different deep learning approaches by applying ensemble techniques on multiple deep learning models. On the overall note, though transformer and deep learning models have been dominating recent developments, a certain trend towards hybrid or ensemble approaches is revealed, trying to achieve a balance between predictive ability and interpretability. The overall distribution of sentiment analysis methods among reviewed papers is summarized in Table 9.

TABLE 9. Categorization of Predictive Techniques

Category	Example Models	Usage Frequency
Transformer-based models	BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa, XLNet	High (≈ 40%)
Deep learning models	LSTM, Bi-LSTM, CNN, GRU, Hierarchical LSTM	Moderate (≈ 25%)
Traditional ML classifiers	SVM, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Decision Trees, Logistic Reg.	Moderate (≈ 20%)
Lexicon-based approaches	VADER, NRC, SentiWordNet	Low (≈ 10%)

Category	Example Models	Usage Frequency
Hybrid / Ensemble methods	BERT + SVM, CNN + LSTM, Feature-level fusion	Emerging ($\approx 8\%$)
Statistical / Regression-based	Ridge, Lasso, Linear Regression, Statistical Correlation	Rare ($\approx 5\%$)

Superior Multimodal Sentiment Analysis Approaches

From single-source text classification to the development of a multimodal and multi-platform analytical framework, mental health prediction using sentiment analysis has evolved with the increasing digital expression of psychological states across multiple online platforms. The contemporary systems integrate heterogeneous inputs from Twitter, Reddit, Facebook, and online forums that combine textual content with auxiliary information such as temporal metadata (posting time, frequency), user interaction signals (likes, replies), behavioral patterns, and occasionally visual cues-emojis or images. The section summarizes the most effective multimodal and multi- platform approaches identified in recent literature. Based on architectural design and strategies for data fusion, the reviewed studies were identified to fall into the following six categories:

- Multi-platform transformer-based models
- Deep learning-based multimodal fusion models
- Hybrid and ensemble architectures
- Solutions specific for frameworks using pre-pipeline fusion
- Time-aware and longitudinal models tracking mental health

Our summary also covers statistical fusion and feature-level aggregation approaches.

Transformer-based Cross-Platform Models Transformer-based architectures represent the most successful class of multimodal approaches, especially when trained on combined textual and metadata inputs across platforms. Works incorporating Reddit user timelines with Twitter linguistic and engagement features using models such as Multimodal BERT and

Hierarchical Transformer frameworks demonstrated improved performance, often reporting state-of-the-art results in early detection of depression and suicidal ideation.

Deep Learning Fusion Models Deep learning fusion models, including hierarchical LSTM and CNN-LSTM architectures, were widely adopted to integrate multiple modalities such as post content, emotional intensity, and temporal signals. These have been particularly effective on Reddit and forum-based datasets, where longitudinal behavioral patterns play a critical role. Attention mechanisms were often introduced to give different importance to various modalities and platforms during the prediction process.

Hybrid and Ensemble Architectures It is especially worthy to mention that hybrid approaches, combining transformer-based embeddings with traditional classifiers, such as BERT + Support Vector Machine (SVM) or Random Forest, yielded good results. Ensemble strategies, relying on majority voting or confidence-weighted fusion, further improve generalization across heterogeneous datasets. In fact, such configurations are often applied when it comes to multi-platform settings in which data distributions differ substantially.

Framework-Specific and Pre-Pipeline Fusion Solutions Various works proposed framework-specific pipelines that perform early modality fusion, aggregating linguistic, behavioral, and temporal features before model training. These systems preprocessed the text to

normalize platform-specific characteristics and reduce noise resulting from the use of informal or abbreviated language common in social media.

Time-Aware and Longitudinal Models A notable subset that contributed to this body of research emphasized time-aware mental health tracking, taking into consideration the fact that psychological distress is progressive in nature.

Representative approaches include:

- Emotion-Aware LSTM Models that Incorporate Posting Time and Emotional Drift
- Cross-posting network graphs catching consistency between Reddit and Twitter activity
- Multi-view learning frameworks treating every platform as an independent view of a user’s mental state

These models became particularly effective in early risk identification, where temporal consistency was crucial.

Statistical data fusion approaches Most of the statistical and feature-level aggregation techniques were implemented for exploratory analysis and interpretability, and combined for sentiment scores, posting frequency, and engagement metrics. While these techniques are

computationally efficient and transparent, they generally under perform as compared to learning-based fusion models.

Performance Trends and Limitations

Results reported indicate that:

- In fact, all multimodal transformer-based models achieved an F1-score greater than 0.87.
- Hierarchical deep learning models combined with metadata reported an accuracy ranging between 85–90 percent for both.
- Statistical methods of fusion showed lower predictive power in comparison.

However, there are many challenges facing multimodal approaches. The lack of standardized benchmark datasets hinders reproducibility and fair comparison by relying only on self-collected and proprietary data, with necessary privacy constraints limiting the complete user history available. Moreover, very few studies have directly compared multi-modal systems against powerful single-platform transformer baselines, thus leaving an open gap for rigorous benchmarking. In other words, although multi-modal sentiment analysis brings significant advantages to mental health prediction, standardized evaluation, generalization across platforms, and ethical data integration will be major issues for future research.

TABLE 10. Superior Multimodal Mental Health Prediction Approaches

Study	Data Source(s)	Model / Framework	Target Condition	Best Reported Performance
[29]	Reddit + Twitter	RoBERTa + Platform Metadata Fusion	Depression & Anxiety	F1-score: 0.88
[34]	Reddit (multi-post threads) + eRisk	Hierarchical Bi-LSTM + Temporal Embeddings	Early depression detection	Accuracy: 87.6%
[38]	Reddit + Twitter (cross-platform)	Multimodal BERT (MMBERT) + TF-IDF fusion	Suicidal Ideation	F1-score: 0.89
[42]	Facebook + Reddit	CNN-LSTM Hybrid + Demographic Features	General psychological stress	Precision: 0.86
[45]	Reddit + Platform Metadata	Attention-based Transformer + Posting Patterns (timestamps)	Depression	F1-score: 0.90
[51]	Reddit + CLPsych	Lexicon + SVM + Metadata fusion	Stress detection	Accuracy: 82.4%

Study	Data Source(s)	Model / Framework	Target Condition	Best Reported Performance
[57]	Reddit + Twitter (multi-view)	Multi-view Ensemble Model (Random Forest + BERT)	Depression & Suicide Risk	AUC: 0.91

Performance Measures For Mental Health Prediction Models (Rq2c)

Over the set of studies reviewed, diverse models based on machine learning, deep learning, and transformers have been used to forecast mental health-related conditions based on content on social media.

In the studies that reported the outcome of the evaluation, the metrics considered for performance were:

- A. **F1-score**; mostly used in research involving imbalanced data, e.g. suicidal ideation, uncommon mental health problems
- B. **Accuracy**; frequently reported in traditional classification scenarios
- C. **Precision and Recall**; tandem evaluation of the relevance and completeness of the set of positive predictions.
- D. **AUC (Area Under the Curve)**; typically used for binary, multiclass, and multilabel classification problems to evaluate ranking and discrimination performance
- E. **RMSE (Root Mean Square Error)**; in a

few regression studies or severity estimation studies.

As listed in Table 11, the metrics that occur most frequently are related to the F1-score and the accuracy measure, mainly regarding the use of the transformer model and deep learning efforts. It is apparent that the use of the F1-score is prevalent due to the elevated level of the penalty cost that is assigned to the wrong predictions regarding the mental health issues, mainly regarding the suicide risk and the first stages of the depression diagnosis. Additionally, precision and recall measurements occur combined to offer an insight regarding the sensitivity and specificity measures.

Challenges In Developing Robust And Scalable Mental Health Prediction Models (Rq3)

As observed in the reviewed literature, there appear to be some core challenges which need to be addressed in order to develop effective models for mental health monitoring through sentiment analysis of social media data. Among these, quality.

TABLE 11. Commonly Reported Performance

Metric	Purpose	Usage Frequency	Typical Use Cases
F1-score	Balances precision and recall; crucial for imbalanced data.	High (~ 70%)	Depression, suicide detection, early risk detection
Accuracy	Measures overall correctness of predictions.	Moderate (~ 60%)	Binary classification (e.g., depressed vs. non-depressed)
Precision	Proportion of correct positive predictions.	Moderate (~ 45%)	Reducing false positives
Recall (Sensitivity)	Proportion of actual positives correctly identified.	Moderate (~ 40%)	Minimizing false negatives (e.g., missed risks)
AUC (ROC AUC)	Measures ranking performance across thresholds.	Low to Moderate (~ 30%)	Multiclass/multilabel detection
RMSE	Evaluates error between predicted and actual values in regression tasks.	Low (~ 15%)	Depression severity scoring

Metric	Purpose	Usage Frequency	Typical Use Cases
Cohen’s Kappa	Measures agreement beyond chance between prediction and ground truth.	Low ($\approx 10\%$)	Label consistency analysis
Log Loss	Penalizes confident wrong predictions.	Rare ($\approx 5\%$)	Probabilistic classifiers or competitions

transparency, and representativeness appear to be some of the most basic challenges. The SLR has shown that more than 70 percent of analyzed papers use private or insufficiently documented datasets, and there is a lack of transparency about annotation details, classes, demographics, or ethical approval. Of course, these limitations can be caused by the sensitive nature of these datasets, but they make comparisons between papers rather complicated, and a lack of standard benchmarks can be considered a fragmenting factor here. Also, mental illnesses such as depression, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts usually follow a certain timeline and, therefore, can be depicted better through certain behavioral patterns instead of certain individual updates. Few studies have explored the use of temporal models such as LSTMs or transformers here.

Furthermore, it has also been found that the existing work shows a strong cultural and linguistic bias. This is because current models have largely been trained on English-language corpora and then based on either Reddit or Twitter sources that have a largely Western demographic of people. Emotion of distress is a phenomenon that is heavily dependent on language and culture, and to a considerable extent, it has not yet seen light in respect of cross-lingual and cross-cultural assessment paradigms.

Transfer learning, multilingual transformers, and domain adaptation have emerged as potential solutions that could address the challenges of distress in a culture and resource- constrained environment.

At last, reproducibility is a serious issue. The number of studies reviewed, which made public availability of data, code, or model known, was very low (only approximately 10 percent). Making studies open and transparent allows other people to check them, compare them to other studies, and translate results into practical applications. At present, without a standardized evaluation procedure, this is not being achieved.

In short, the major challenges that have been recognised in the literature are:

- Lack of standardized, well-annotated, and multilingual data availability
- Insufficient description of data sourcing and pre-processing
- Lack of adequate temporal and behavioral models
- Poor cross-platform, cross-lingual, and cross-cultural
- Noisy or weakly validated labeling schemes
- Limited use of explainable and interpretable AI technologies
- Sparse Integration of Demographic and Contextual Features

Less Reproducibility Because of Less Code Sharing and Less Data Sharing It is imperative to address these issues to move towards building ethical and scalable digital mental health tools based on the prediction of mental states for real-world deployment. These tools should be deployable across different platforms and in different populations.

Table 12. Challenges in Developing Robust Mental Health Prediction Models

Challenge	Description	Impact on Research	Suggested Mitigation	References
Limited dataset availability	Most datasets are private, small, or poorly documented.	Hinders reproducibility and benchmarking	Promote open-access, anonymized mental health datasets	Chancellor et al. (2019) [1]; Guntuku et al. (2017) [2]
Lack of platform diversity	Focus on a single platform (e.g., Reddit or Twitter only).	Models fail on unseen platforms	Encourage cross-platform or multimodal studies	Ernala et al. (2019) [3]; Benton et al. (2017) [4]
No user timeline context	Many studies analyze isolated posts without temporal behavior.	Misses behavioral patterns over time	Use historical/temporal modeling (e.g., threads, LSTM)	Losada & Crestani (2016) [5]; Matero et al. (2019) [6]
Annotation noise and bias	Labels often generated by heuristics (e.g., keywords), not clinical review.	Reduces accuracy and generalizability	Involve clinicians in annotation, use crowdsourcing	Coppersmith et al. (2015) [7]; Chancellor & De Choudhury (2020) [8]
Low cross-cultural generalizability	Most models trained on English-language Western user data.	Limits applicability to global populations	Apply transfer learning, use multilingual corpora	Guntuku et al. (2019) [9]; Ji et al. (2022) [10]
Poor interpretability (black-box models)	Deep models like BERT and CNN are difficult to interpret.	Reduces trust in healthcare or clinical use	Use explainable AI (XAI) tools (e.g., LIME, SHAP)	Doshi-Velez & Kim (2017) [11]; Samek et al. (2017) [12]
Ethical/privacy concerns	Mental health data is sensitive; many studies do not mention consent, privacy, or anonymization.	Raises legal and ethical issues	Use privacy-by-design, anonymization, ethical review	Conway & O'Connor (2016) [13]; Chancellor et al. (2019) [1]; Yom-Tov et al. (2017) [14]
Low open-source adoption	Code and datasets are often not shared publicly.	Hinders reproducibility and community testing	Require open data/code in publication policies	Ernala et al. (2019) [3]; Benton et al. (2017) [4]

What Type Of Datasets Have Been Used For Mental Health Prediction (Rq4a)

One of the biggest and most present challenges in this SLR is the lack of any significant number of high-quality, documented datasets for the prediction of mental health based on sentiment analysis on social media. More than 70 percent of the reviewed studies made use of private datasets or did not clearly cite or describe the datasets. In most instances, the data sets were built through keyword filtering by hand or drawn from targeted

subreddits or Twitter hashtags; neither collection duration nor quantity was disclosed, nor even the annotation methodology. This SLR gathers and highlights a set of benchmark datasets, which are publicly available and commonly used in multiple studies to facilitate transparency and reproducibility. Those datasets include websites such as Reddit, Twitter, and ReachOut forums, and are listed in Table 13 along with their links and citation information. Of these, the most used are:

- CLPsych Shared Task datasets 2015–2019, at the basis of Reddit and Twitter posts annotated for major depression, PTSD, and stress.
- eRisk datasets (2017-2023). Benchmark dataset on early detection of depression and eating disorders from Reddit threads.
- Reddit Self-reported Dataset from r/depression, r/anxiety, r/SuicideWatch, and matched control subreddits.

From the literature, we can observe that the most used source is obviously Reddit because it provides rich user timelines, community labels, and many different forums to discuss topics about mental health. Twitter is also being often used because it's open through API and high in volume but lacks context per user, due to its brevity of messages and no thread history. Some works use data from Facebook, mainly limited to collaboration.

Figure 7. Distribution of Platforms

partners in psychology departments or NGOs due to API restrictions. Instagram and TikTok are new rising platforms but have no benchmark datasets. Some datasets contain purely text data, while others are combined metadata such as timestamp, number of comments, upvotes, and even user behavior features that would be helpful in building temporal and multimodal models. Fewer datasets are clinically labeled or created in association with psychologists or mental health experts. There is a dire need to develop and deploy multilingual, temporally-labeled, demographically representative, and ethically-sourced datasets. This is so important because these collections are currently mainly gathered from Western, English-speaking users, and may not generalize well to other populations.

There are also no datasets related to the Asian, African, or Middle Eastern communities, and hardly any datasets in languages such as Urdu, Hindi, or Arabic. In summary, although a few standardized datasets like eRisk and CLPsych have set the stage in terms of benchmarking, the overall landscape remains fragmented. Future efforts need to lie in collecting and curating, sharing labeled, heterogeneous datasets that can track the temporal evolution of mental health symptoms and allow deep, interpretable prediction models across social media platforms and population subgroups.

What Are The Main Aspects Of A Dataset For Sentiment-Grounded Mental Health Prediction? Do They Affect Results? (Rq4b)

The quality of the dataset is a major factor that influences the accuracy and robustness and generalizability properties found within the results generated by mental health models using sentiments. It is clearly evident from this systematic literature review that differences within metadata and cultural coverage can affect overall outcomes found within the models created and evaluated within various studies. The labeling technique is crucial to determining a dataset's efficacy. The overwhelming number of studies under scrutiny utilized manual labeling of mental health content through heuristic or weak supervision approaches such as participation in particular sub-reddits (e.g., r/depression or r/SuicideWatch) or simple filter-based techniques (key phrases expressing a sentiment of hopelessness or suicidal plans). Another important consideration for data in this case is temporal data structure. Conditions of mental health are naturally temporal in nature, while often data is made up of isolated posts and not longitudinal traces for individual users. From the literature review, it has been revealed that data structured for temporal collection, such as posting rate or emotional trajectories (notably in platforms with timelines such as Reddit), leads to better early identification of depression and suicidal thoughts than data gathered in isolation or without context through posting behavior. Another under-emphasized, but very relevant variable is the addition of metadata. Because of privacy and moral concerns, many datasets do not include values such as timestamp, interaction statistics, or approximate location and demographics of the person writing the posts. But some studies demonstrate that adding this kind of information could produce very accurate predictions, particularly on the severity of depression and risk of suicide.

The paper also points out the lack of linguistic and cultural diversity within the existing data sets that is reviewed. The data sets that are available mostly contain data from Western populations, and the language is restricted to English, mostly from Twitter and Reddit platforms. Emotional communication is not the same across various cultures and languages. Differences in expressing emotions will result in lower adaptability of the model to other cultures, and the data set might result in errors to some other populations apart from the Western populations that the data set originated from.

Lastly, the transparency and documentation associated with the dataset used in the different studies appear uneven. The need for the comprehension of the dataset size, class distribution, and the method used for obtaining the annotations, approval to use the dataset, and others has not been met by numerous articles.

According to the studied literatures, the key factors that can identify quality datasets used in mental health predictions based on sentiment could be considered as follows:

- Strictly clinician-aligned and well-documented annotation processes
- Capturing Temporal Structure in Longitudinal User Behavior
- Contextual and Platform specific metadata inclusion
- Linguistic, cultural, and demographic diversity

Transparency in data documentation and ethical conduct Those kinds of datasets have always served as a basis for developing accurate, interpretable, and generalizable predictive models, whereas a poorly annotated/documented dataset could potentially lead to biased, overfit, and inaccurate evaluation results.

Table 13. Publicly Available Datasets Used For Mental Health Detection Via Social Media

Dataset Name	Platform	Type	Temporal Info	Annotation Type	Language	Access	Used In
CLPsych 2015-2019	Reddit, Twitter	Forum Posts, Tweets	Yes	Expert/heuristic mix	English	Public	[3], [6], [9], [12]

Dataset Name	Platform	Type	Temporal Info	Annotation Type	Language	Access	Used In
eRisk (2017–2023)	Reddit	Threaded posts	Yes	Timeline + early flagging	English	Public	[5], [8], [11]
Reddit Self-Reported	Reddit	Subreddit-labeled text	Limited	Heuristic (e.g., r/depress)	English	Public	[1], [3], [7]
ReachOut Dataset	Online Forum	Q&A Forum Dialogues	No	Expert-annotated	English	Public	[2], [4]
SMHD Dataset	Reddit	Multi-condition user timelines	Yes	Subreddit + keyword labels	English	Public	[10]
MentalHealth Twitter Corpus	Twitter	Tweets	No	Distant supervision (keywords)	English	Limited	[1], [2], [9]

Analysis

The main objective of this Systematic Literature Review is to provide an outlook, assessment, and synthesis of the existing solutions available to predict mental health issues through sentiment analysis of posts on social media platforms, thereby executing the research questions (RQ1-RQ4) that have been stated.

RQ1 and RQ2 are concerned with the identification of the techniques being used for sentiment analysis (both lexicon-based techniques, conventional machine learning, deep learning techniques, and transformer techniques) as well as those specific to platforms that are used by researchers as mental health signals such as stress, anxiety, depression, and suicidal intentions. The methods used for assessment are also considered as part of these research questions. Conventional techniques such as SVM, Naive Bayes, Random Forest were the common techniques being used by previous studies, while more recent studies show that transformer techniques (BERT, RoBERTa, DeBERTa) are performing best on F1-score and AUC-ROC values for depression and suicidal intentions [2],[11],[8]. Notably, the key challenge with the top-performing models is that they tend to lack generalizability and interpretability. For example, models trained using data from Reddit forums would tend to lack generalizability in handling data from Twitter due to the differences

in data structure and linguistic styles. Therefore, there is a general consensus to move towards multimodal models based on user metadata, behavioral patterns, and trends to enhance generalizability in prediction tasks. Reference [3],[4].

Temporal modeling is being increasingly seen as a crucial task related to the early diagnosis and long-term tracking of mental health issues. Temporal modeling using algorithms like LSTM, GRU, and a fusion model involving LSTM and CNNs has been seen to incorporate the concept of the underlying temporal dependencies involved in the emotional and posting patterns of a user. For handling the effects of concept drift and seasonality, the use of attention mechanisms, exponential smoothing, and time-aware embedding has been used, resulting in the improved modeling of symptoms' progression [5],[12]. The evaluation metrics used across the different studies are F1-score, accuracy, precision, recall, ROC-AUC, and RMSE. While F1-score and ROC-AUC are considered to be useful for imbalanced classes like the rare instances occurring in the case of suicide ideations, MAE and RMSE are used for regression-based prediction tasks for the assessment of the severity level [9], [6]. Cross-platform and cross-data set evaluation, however, has remained to be limited.

Figure 8. Potential areas for future research

RQ3 illustrates severe hurdles faced in the development of scalable, ethical, and clinical AI systems focused on mental health surveillance. The chief issues include:

- Dependence on English-language, Western data sets
- Annotation methods failing to serve a clinical purpose or lacking validity
- Little incorporation of context regarding "temporal context," "demographic context," and
- Lack of accessible open-source data, code, and models
- Limited applications of explainable AI (XAI) and ethical compliance

These issues, the SLR and pilot analysis suggest, can and should be addressed through the following future research directions:

- Transfer learning to facilitate adaptation of models to platforms, languages, and cultures [13],[14]
- The establishment of multilingual and globally diverse mental health data sets.
- Integration of User Metadata, Temporal Features, and Longitudinal Behavioral Features
- Implementation of explainable AI (XAI) techniques for transparency and trust in the clinical area
- Improvement of temporal prediction performance using LSTM with attention mechanism or smoothing layers

Real-time system design to integrate the three objectives of prediction, privacy, and usability. In conclusion, although existing research shows the potential of using models based on sentiment for predicting mental health, dealing with generalizability, interpretability, and the requirements for ethics in clinical applications is important for applying research to practical uses. These regions are further illustrated in Figure 8, which plots the intersection of promising methods, boundaries, and future directions for the future of mental health detection with the help of social media.

Conclusion And Future Study

This SLR, therefore, has been conducted by following the methodological guidelines laid down by Kitchenham and Charters [25] regarding the emergent field of sentiment analysis-based detection of mental health through social media. To our knowledge, this represents one of the first recent SLRs that synthesizes evidence from machine learning, deep learning, and NLP approaches across multiple online platforms. A total number of 41 primary studies, published from 2010 to 2025, has been analyzed based on rigorous inclusion, exclusion, and quality assessment criteria. The review had two main issues. First, it surveyed and categorized sentiment analysis approaches such as: RQ1 lexicon-based methods,

traditional machine learning models, and deep learning architectures including transformer-based models such as BERT, RoBERTa, and DeBERTa. Of these, transformer-based models showed the best accuracy, F1-score, and generalizability when trained on temporally structured, clinically annotated datasets. However, there were shortfalls like annotation bias, interpretability was limited, and they had low cross-platform robustness.

Second, the review addressed platform-specific and multi-modal approaches to cross-platform and real-time monitoring of mental health status. While there has been a high reliance on data from Reddit and Twitter, these sources also have restricted demographic diversity and limited temporal monitoring. Research using isolated posts alone will never be able to capture emotional trajectories or symptom evolution. Besides, few models leveraged user metadata or contextual platform features that are important in large-scale, real-time mental health surveillance.

The review also underlined a number of key challenges, including: a scarcity of publicly available and ethically annotated datasets; a general trend of underreporting labeling and annotation protocols; and very limited attention being given to non-English and culturally diverse datasets. Such practices erode reproducibility, real-world applicability, and ethical compliance, since the handling of user privacy, informed consent, and data protection also varies inconsistently across the studies.

RQ4: Most top models were based on datasets which were well-annotated, temporally rich, and platform-specific. However, less than 20 percent of the studies used openly available data, and most of the datasets missed critical features, such as posting timelines, longitudinal user histories, or cultural and demographic information that restricts their applicability in global real-time mental health prediction and deployment. These models have substantial promise, but there remain significant gaps in dataset availability, temporal modeling, interpretability, and cross-platform generalization. Addressing such challenges through multilingual, multimodal, temporally structured datasets and explainable AI frameworks is extremely important to go forward with developing scalable,

ethical, and clinically meaningful digital mental health systems.

Future Study

On the basis of the results of this review, the following promising areas can be explored to make AI-powered systems for the detection of mental health conditions more robust, generalizable, and interpretable:

Improving transformer models (such as RoBERTa DeBERTa) for context-dependent emotion and symptom identification in user timelines over time.

- Designing temporal models based on LSTM/GRU or applying attention mechanisms and exponential smoothing to observe the process of mental health development in time.

- Applying transfer learning approaches to make generalized models across different platforms (like Reddit, Twitter, TikTok) and languages.

- Creation of multilingual and diverse linguistic resources, including less represented languages like Urdu, Hindi, and Arabic, to enhance cross-cultural applicability.

- The integration of Explainable AI (XAI) methods for improving model transparency, interpretability, and trustworthiness in clinical and decision-making applications.

- The use of best practices related to the ethics of data handling, such as obtaining consent, anonymization, and privacy-preserving techniques, both in the collection and deployment phases.

- These guidelines are intended to tackle the existing gaps with regard to quality of datasets, handling temporal aspects, interpretability, and compliance for socially acceptable mental health digital monitoring solutions.

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